

D9.4: Knowledge management plan

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1 Introduction

XR4Human will produce knowledge which will be openly shared and freely accessible. Note that knowledge produced in the form of research data is not covered in this plan (rf. D9.1). XR4Human does not utilise or rely on any foreground IP held and contributed by the partners. This section describes the knowledge management processes in relation to publications and all textual deliverables, including training materials.

2 Open accessibility of publications and other textual deliverables

Publications and all other textual materials including training materials will be produced within the context of the Work Package tasks of the XR4Human project. All textual deliverables are to be categorised as Public and, after delivery to the European Commission via the Funding and Tenders portal, will be made available on the project website and in the Embassy of Good Science. These will also be available on the Commission website. All publications will conform with the Horizon Europe and the Grant Agreement requirements for open access. This means that publications, for example, will be published in open access journals making them freely available online with no restrictions on use and with an appropriate open access license. If possible in the relevant publication outlets, a CC BY Creative Commons Attribution Licence (Creative Commons — Attribution 2.0 Generic — CC BY 2.0, n.d.) will be chosen, or if the publication does not allow this, the slightly more restrictive CC BY-NC (Creative Commons — Attribution-NonCommercial 2.0 Generic — CC BY-NC 2.0, n.d.) license will be used. All publications will also be deposited in relevant open access repositories such as the national repositories of the participating countries.

3 Authorship and Contributorship

Authorship will be agreed and documented by the Work Package leader as early as possible during the development of a particular publication or deliverable. This agreement will specify who qualifies as authors and the order of authors. If the order of authors cannot be specified at an early stage, e.g. if the magnitude of contributions to the research is not yet fixed, the agreement will specify the process and criteria for determining the authorship order.

The criteria for qualification as an author will be the standard criteria within the biomedical field as specified by the International Council of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) guidelines and by the practical interpretation of these guidelines. Hence, citing ICMJE, one is an author if all the following criteria are present:

- Substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work; AND
- Drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content; AND
- Final approval of the version to be published; AND
- Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved (ICMJE | Recommendations | Defining the Role of Authors and Contributors, n.d.)

The ICMJE also adds that “an author should be able to identify which co-authors are responsible for specific other parts of the work” and that “authors should have confidence in the integrity of the contributions of their co-authors.”

3.1 Defining Consortium Authorship Beyond the XR4Human Project

For an inclusive authorship policy, future proof of the authorship and to maintain the integrity of publications beyond the duration of the XR4Human grant, the following principles will be applied:

3.2 Consortium authorship for publications that involve all partners

The consortium authorship will be defined under the “The XR4Human Project” for publications or deliverables published by responsible work package leaders/authors.

- Where appropriate “The XR4Human Project” will either be listed as an author (and ‘The XR4Human Project Authorship’ be listed towards the back of the paper) or elsewhere, as appropriate, “The XR4Human Project” is simply acknowledged.

3.3 Contributorship and Guarantorship in XR4Human Consortium

- **Contributorship:** Contributors must meet at least 4 criteria for authorship to be listed in the publication or deliverable (See 1.2). The work package leaders/author(s) responsible will be first listed at the top. A “non-author contributors” list will follow, stating who has contributed and details of their contributions which may not be as much as the responsible work package leaders/author (s). This will ensure that any contributor(s) will appear in online searches after the end of the project.
- **Guarantorship:** The Coordinating institution, USN will be listed as the main guarantor of publications under the XR4Human project. USN will take full responsibility for the management of studies conducted, data access, and the decision to publish.

3.4 Disagreement about authorship

As described in the preceding section, the output development process involves reaching an authorship agreement at an early stage in the development of each output according to the standard authorship criteria. If, however, an authorship dispute later arises in relation to an output this will be mediated by the Project Coordinator (PC), or if the PC is involved in the publication or has another conflict of interest, by a Work Package Leader appointed by the Steering Committee. The outcome of the mediation will be binding to all parties.

REFERENCE LIST

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